

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: INSIGHTS FROM HEALTH CARE STUDENTS

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to explore student perceptions regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education. AI can play a role in various aspects of higher education, including the teaching-learning process, admissions, placements, and administrative functions. This paper highlights the perceptions of Para medical students enrolled in Allied Health sciences programs on the use of AI. An online questionnaire was used to gather both quantitative and qualitative responses from 600 students. Statistical methods, including ordination regression and correlation analysis, were applied to interpret the data. The qualitative responses provided valuable insights into students' viewpoints. The findings reveal that students perceive AI as an effective tool for enhancing the teaching-learning process and academic administration, but they believe it should not be applied to certain areas such as admissions, examinations, and placements.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Student Perceptions, Higher Education, Business Management, Teaching-Learning Process, Academic Administration, Admissions, Placements, Examinations, Statistical Analysis, Quantitative and Qualitative Research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Health professional business have reported significant improvements in efficiency by incorporating AI as a computerized decision-making tool. However, despite its potential, AI adoption in higher education remains limited.

While AI offers substantial benefits across various higher education processes, most institutions have yet to fully leverage its capabilities. Even in top-tier business schools, AI integration in institutional processes has been minimal. This reluctance is primarily due to concerns over high investment costs and the perception of AI as a complex tool, often associated with advanced scientists and technologists. However, previous studies suggest that implementing AI across different educational processes can significantly enhance institutional efficiency.

The uniqueness of this study lies in its focus on a key yet often overlooked stakeholder in the education system—students. Their perspectives on AI implementation in different academic areas have rarely been examined. What are students' opinions on AI-driven selection in the admission process? How would they perceive AI integration in the teaching-learning process, potentially as a partial substitute for faculty? What are their views on AI-driven placement procedures? How would they respond to AI handling administrative tasks such as leave management and class exemptions? What are their thoughts on AI-based evaluation and grading of assignments? This study aims to address these questions and provide insights into student perspectives on AI in education. Its findings will assist educational leaders and planners in identifying the most suitable areas for AI implementation based on student preferences, ensuring that investments are directed toward areas where AI is perceived as most beneficial, rather than being allocated to less favorable applications.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Coppin, Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the ability of machines to adapt to new situations, manage dynamic environments, solve problems, respond to queries, develop plans, and perform various tasks that typically require human intelligence [1]. AI represents a global revolution that is anticipated to play a crucial role in shaping the future [2]. Advances in AI tools have led to their integration into decision-support systems across various applications, significantly influencing decision-making processes [3]. Businesses are being transformed, and workflows are being restructured due to AI, fostering extensive collaboration between humans and machines [4].

The rise of big data, sophisticated algorithms, and enhanced computing and storage capabilities has solidified AI's role in augmenting human contributions [5]. Recent advancements in big data technologies and supercomputing have strengthened AI's capabilities, establishing a complementary relationship between AI and human decision-making within organizations [6]. A hybrid approach that combines AI with human decision-making can positively impact the quality of organizational decisions [7]. By decreasing biases in human interactions and increasing productivity, AI use has improved the candidate experience [8].

AI has a lot of potential in higher education, particularly in fields like admissions, career services, and learning management. AI is viewed as a technique to increase justice and lessen bias in the admissions process [9]. To differentiate themselves from rivals and

promote long-term growth, innovative colleges might think about implementing AI [9]. AI has the ability to tailor learning experiences, which can lead to improved academic outcomes [10]. It has been employed in tutoring platforms to offer immediate help to struggling students [11]. The applications of AI in higher education span across learning, teaching, and administrative tasks [12]. It can take over responsibilities traditionally performed by instructors while also enhancing student learning through personalization [13]. Additionally, AI can be used for grading and assessments based on specific rubrics and standards [14]. Its integration into higher education has led to more effective teaching and richer learning experiences for students [15].

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted using a structured questionnaire, with data collected through convenience sampling. A total of 620 questionnaires were distributed to Allied Health Sciences students, of which 600 were deemed fully usable for analysis. To gather student opinions, the study employed a five-point Likert scale. The main question asked of students was their opinion on the use of AI in academia. They were surveyed on whether AI should be integrated into academic processes, with their responses captured using a five-point scale:

- 1 – Strongly Disagree
- 2 – Disagree
- 3 – Neutral
- 4 – Agree
- 5 – Strongly Agree.

Students were further asked to express their views on AI usage across various academic domains, including the teaching-learning process, administrative processes, examinations, placements, and admissions. The study examined the following null hypothesis in order to figure out how students felt about AI in higher education. **H₀: There is no significant difference in student perceptions regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence across different academic processes.**

4. FINDINGS & DISCUSSION

Table 1 provides a summary of the collected data, indicating that there were no missing values, with responses obtained from a total of 662 participants. The data reveals that 81.6% of respondents (47.5% selecting "Strongly Agree" and 34.10% selecting "Agree") believe that AI and its tools should be integrated into academia. The table also presents the percentage distribution of responses for all questions. Regarding AI implementation in specific academic areas:

- **Teaching and Learning Process:** 70.9% of students (Strongly Agree and Agree) support its use.

- **Academic Administration Process:** 74.52% of students (Strongly Agree and Agree) favour AI adoption.
- **Examination Process:** Only 33.00% of students (Strongly Agree and Agree) support AI implementation.
- **Placement Process:** 33.92 % of students (Strongly Agree and Agree) approve of AI usage.
- **Admission Process:** Similarly, 33.9% of students (Strongly Agree and Agree) endorse AI integration.

Table 1: Summary of Data Collected

Aspect	Scale	Percentage (%)
AI should be used in Academia	Strongly Disagree	3.33%
	Disagree	3.20%
	Neutral	16.01%
	Agree	43.71%
	Strongly Agree	33.82%
AI need to be included in the process of teaching and learning	Strongly Disagree	3.32%
	Disagree	3.21%
	Neutral	22.81%
	Agree	38.40%
	Strongly Agree	32.50%
AI should be used in Academic Administration Process	Strongly Disagree	3.30%
	Disagree	3.21%
	Neutral	19.01%
	Agree	43.11%
	Strongly Agree	31.41%
AI should be used in Examination Process	Strongly Disagree	13.30%
	Disagree	23.21%
	Neutral	30.51%
	Agree	21.60%
	Strongly Agree	11.4%
AI should be used in Placement Process	Strongly Disagree	3.33%
	Disagree	23.21%
	Neutral	39.61%
	Agree	22.01%
	Strongly Agree	11.91%
AI should be used in Admission Process	Strongly Disagree	3.32%
	Disagree	13.2%
	Neutral	29.6%
	Agree	19.0%
	Strongly Agree	14.9%
Total Respondents	Valid Responses	600 (100%)
	Missing Responses	0
	Total Responses	600

To test the hypothesis, the model fit summary was analysed, and the null hypothesis was statistically evaluated. Table II displays the model summary for the ordinal regression analysis.

The null hypothesis was overruled since the data showed a significant value of 0.00. This implies that different students have different opinions about the use of artificial intelligence in different academic procedures in higher Education.

The study explored students' views on incorporating AI and its tools into academia and examined their relationships with teaching and learning, academic administration, examination processes, placements, and admissions through correlation analysis.

Table II: Model Fitting Information for Ordinal Regression

Model	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept Only	1183.2367	—	—	—
Final	1183.2367	12	0.000	0.000

Here is the rephrased text along with a newly formatted table:

Spearman’s Correlation Analysis

Table III highlights the correlation between students' perceptions of AI in academia and its role in the **Teaching and Learning Process**.

The correlation coefficient of **+0.5960** and a significance value of **0.001** indicate a strong positive relationship. The qualitative data further supports the notion that AI can improve teaching methodologies and streamline the learning experience.

Table IV shows Spearman’s correlation coefficient for the relationship between students' views on the use of AI in academia and its application in academic administration.

The correlation coefficient is **+0.574**, with a significance value of **0.003**, indicating a strong positive correlation.

This implies that students who favor the integration of AI in academia also believe that AI can improve administrative processes, making them more efficient.

Table V demonstrates the correlation between students' views on AI in academia and its implementation in **Examination Administration**.

The correlation coefficient of **-0.641**, with a significance value of **0.000**, suggests a strong negative correlation.

This implies that students are skeptical about using AI for exam evaluation, especially for theoretical or viva-based assessments.

They believe that AI and robotic evaluation systems may not yet be advanced enough to ensure error-free assessments, as these technologies are still evolving.

Table III: Correlation between AI in Academia and Teaching & Learning Process

Spearman's	AI in Academia	AI in Teaching & Learning Process
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.5960(Positive Correlation)
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.001
N	600	600

Table IV: Correlation between AI in Academia and Academic Administration

Spearman's	AI in Academia	AI in Academic Administration Process
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	0.574 (Positive Correlation)
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.003
N	600	600

Table V: Correlation between AI in Academia and Examination Administration

Spearman's	AI in Academia	AI in Examination Administration Process
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-0.641 (Negative Correlation)
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.000
N	600	600

Spearman’s Correlation Analysis: AI in Academia and Placement Process

Table VI displays the Spearman’s correlation coefficient between students' views on AI in academia and its involvement in the placement process. The correlation coefficient of -0.458, with a significance value of 0.002, indicates a moderate negative correlation. This implies that students exhibit skepticism toward the use of AI in the placement process, especially in job selection and interview automation. Qualitative data further suggests that students perceive AI and robotic systems as not yet fully reliable for conducting job interviews. They believe these technologies are still in their early stages of development and may increase errors in candidate selection.

Table VI: Correlation Between AI in Academia and Placement Process

Spearman's	AI in Academia	AI in Placement Process
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-0.458 (Negative Correlation)
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.002
N	600	600

Spearman’s Correlation Analysis: AI in Academia and Admission Process

Table VII presents the Spearman’s correlation coefficient between students' views on AI in academia and its role in the admission process. With a correlation coefficient of -0.156 and a significance value of 0.01, the results indicate a slight negative correlation. This suggests that students are somewhat hesitant about incorporating AI into the admission process, particularly for automating student selection and interviews. Qualitative data further reveals that students believe AI and robotic systems may lead to errors in candidate evaluation, as these technologies are still in the early stages of development.

Table VII: Correlation between AI in Academia and Admission Process

Spearman's	AI in Academia	AI in Admission Process
Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-0.156 (Slight Negative Correlation)
Sig. (2-tailed)	—	0.01
N	600	600

5. CONCLUSION

With the increasing prominence of AI across various Health professional business processes, this study explored its role in higher education, focusing on student perceptions. In addition to quantitative findings, qualitative feedback was also gathered to provide deeper insights. According to student perceptions, AI is well-suited for enhancing the teaching-learning process, aligning with existing literature that highlights its benefits for both instructors and learners. Additionally, students expressed a positive outlook on integrating AI into academic administration processes. However, the study found strong opposition to the use of AI in the examination process, as students were uncertain about its accuracy. Similarly, they showed moderate resistance to AI implementation in the placement process, though they acknowledged that advancements in AI technology could improve its viability in the future. Students also expressed reservations about using AI in the admission process, citing concerns over its accuracy in candidate selection. In conclusion, students generally support the use of AI in teaching, learning, and academic administration. However, they remain skeptical about its application in examinations, admissions, and placements. Therefore, AI should be selectively implemented in higher education, focusing on areas where students perceive its benefits to be the most significant.

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